

Learning Platforms Both of Conventional and Online Educational Systems: Perspectives on Blended Learning

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to find out how using the platform from the perspective of both teachers and students can help to enhance the teaching and learning process at the University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto for Master's Degree Students. The Pandemic gave a lot of benefits in the educational field. As we know online learning has been used since a long time ago supporting teaching and learning material using the website. Many people create an application and modern websites like Zoom, G-meet, on class, etc. That application supported almost everyone because it allowed for the flexible delivery of information via audio-visuals no matter time or place. However, online learning also needs to be implemented to know students' motivation, responsibility, and learning behavior.

Problem-solving that the University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto used was implementing blended learning both online 60% and offline 40%. The data collection was an open-ended questionnaire that delivered questions to one lecturer, one international student, and 7 national students through G-Form. Inductive analysis was utilized using the data. As a result, all of the respondents gave positive and agreement perspectives on blended learning because it could make students learn autonomously, manage time more flexibly, enhance student achievement, and be confident when offline class.

1. Introduction

In 2020, a year that everyone around the globe will never forget a virus whose spread shocked the entire world. Covid-19 is the name given by the virus. The virus caused some changes in the world system. Almost no educational levels in the education sector allow students to enter a school or campus. Even if there are still a number of factors limiting learning, all educational levels must implement online learning whether they are ready for it or not in order to finish the scheduled education program on time. Starting with the lack of suitable human resources, online resources like mobile phones, laptops, and the internet are ineffective because of infrastructural issues that develop during the online learning process.

Online Learning, sometimes known as E-learning, is nothing new. Most of the top universities and institutions in the world have long used this idea. As stated by Abou El Seoud et al., (2014) form of education known as "e-learning" connects teachers and students through a web that is connected to an internet connection or an internal network. Here, teachers and students are connected via the network and the internet. In this instance, the system is similar to a classroom where all learning-related resources, forums, and subjects are available. Likewise a network like the internet or an intranet was utilized to show teachers as well as students the web. E-learning is defined as "the use of electronic media for a variety of learning purposes that range from add-on functions in traditional classrooms to full substitution for the face-to-face meetings by online encounters" by Guri-Rosenblit (2005). Online learning provides resources with excellent search efficiency, access from any location, and engaging interaction for effective learning. Online and offline courses differ significantly in two fundamental ways: psychological value and potential learning importance (Paul & Jefferson, 2019). In addition, Wolverton and Tanner (2019) suggested using simultaneous online dialogues to help students manage their anxiety of speaking in front of an audience on the internet to develop the essential skills of successful online professional communication.

Offline learning can be defined as instruction that takes place online, usually in an educational institution, or classroom. Online learning contrasts with offline learning, occasionally referred to as "conventional learning," the latter's machine learning program works immediately on the data collected, compared to the earlier. A case study conducted by Shentil and Susobhan (2022), academic performance of students who learn offline is slightly better than that of students who learn online. Besides to the literature review, students were interested in online education and thought it improved their professional development. Anxious issues with online learning include stress, emotional well-being, and boredom (Zizka & Probst, 2021).

Covid-19 makes educational setting changed by online learning. Then, some researchers were interested to conduct research about online learning related to its effectiveness, benefit, assessment, and so on. Other researchers have produced similar findings. In order for students to keep their enthusiasm for learning through a pandemic, lecturers must constantly motivate them, Dewanto (2021). Even though, the Pandemic was ended, but some schools or universities still conduct online learning for completing the educational system because that's assessed effectively.

Nowadays, post Covid's advantages have had many good impacts on platforms, applications, the web, and others. Almost school or University has their own application related to online learning platforms for supporting educational settings on themselves. University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto uses the website "On Class" exclusively to encourage online instruction and learning. This website is used to administer assignments, track attendance, administer final exam tests, and more. Additionally, weekend offline learning is still possible to be conducted. A legally permitted educational environment permits a ratio of 60% online learning and 40% offline study. Regarding to this obligation, there is blending learning both of online and offline. This study attempts to investigate how students and teachers' perspective on the platform is being used to enhance how students get educated and how they learn.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Benefits and Drawbacks of Online and Offline Education

There are benefit and drawbacks of blended learning between online versus offline learning. Numerous previous studies have provided mixed results regarding the advantages and disadvantages of online versus offline education systems. In relation to the finding, students find it challenging to ask questions about content they don't comprehend when learning online and tend to lose focus. According to Pratama and Mulyati (2020), the implementation of online learning has a number of problems including low technology mastery, limited access to resources, high spending, poor internet connectivity, and waning teacher and student enthusiasm as a result of growing indifference about this technology.

However, Dewanto (2021) stated that the students think that having offline classes makes it difficult to focus and manage their time. Additionally, Goyal (2012) noted that there are a number of factors to take consideration when putting online learning into practice. Since learning is really a social cognitive process, not all students are going to gain from this approach. In front of a computer, some students can quickly become bored, while others could feel like they have more flexibility to learn. In the speech, Allen et al. (2002) speculate that students' resistance to the using of modern technology may stem from their unwillingness to become familiar with new things that they see as difficult and might not live through to their expectations, allowing them to believe that the technology is unable to replace their classroom activities.

Students are not comfortable to join online class due to some problems that they face but some students feel cozy. However, online learning also provides a number of advantages, according to research by Sadeghi (2019), including the flexibility to choose, the ability to study anywhere and at any time, the ability to save a lot of money, and the elimination of transportation. According to various researches, online learning can produce outcomes that are equivalent to those of offline learning. Regarding to some students' attitude toward the platform that teacher used, Maya et al., (2022) supported that various attitudes about online education is about how the students expressed satisfaction with their results on the assessments and the information presented in the classes. The degree of student confidence comes first. Students often lack the confidence to respond to conversations with teachers or lecturers when learning offline (Husaini, 2020). If statements stated or expressed are incorrect or contrary to the provided content, they worry about being embarrassed. According to Suwartono (2022), the English teacher's enthusiastic response indicates her constancy in the concept that digital technology provides many advantages for EFL learning, including the assessment.

2.2. Blended Learning Models

2.2.1. Rotation of the Lab

According to the "Rotation of Laboratories" blended learning concept, students spend a percentage of their time in a traditional classroom and one lesson in a computer laboratory where they work on their own projects in an online setting. Students can study new material, develop on their prior knowledge, practice a variety of competencies, and complete their own projects online. If this concept is applied in schools, then teachers developing an online environment for student that is common across many courses will

result in the most effective learning. As long as the online environment is appropriate for their age, this blended learning strategy can be used with kids of any age.

2.2.2. Inverted Class

The simplest strategy to use, allows you to introduce interactive work in the classroom while minimizing frontal work (the teacher explains, the students listen). Students learn at home in a virtual setting on their own Internet-connected electronic devices, either getting familiar with the subject matter or reviewing what they have already learned. Through project-based learning, seminars, or other interactive techniques, the class combines and works with the subject. For children in grades 3-5, this blended learning strategy can be applied in the classroom.

2.2.3. Station Rotation

Students must use laptops, tablets, or learning management systems in the classroom in order to implement the most effective blended learning strategy for elementary and high school. According to the type of educational activity—in-person lessons, online learning, and project work—all students are separated into groups. Each group operates in a different station within the classroom. There are many goals for each station: receiving feedback from the teacher when working with a teacher; developing skills for independent work, responsibility, self-control, and learning ability; using knowledge to solve real-world problems; and receiving feedback from others when working on assignments. Students walk from every platform to another throughout the class to visit each one.

2.2.4. Flexible layout

Students' access to more than one sort of learning activity at once is the foundation of a flexible blended learning strategy. Students independently plan their workload, select their study quickly, and create their work schedule. This model primarily operates online. When the student needs guidance, the teacher works with small groups or allow to student work alone. Due to the need for a developed ability of self-organization, this technique is most effective for teaching adults, students, and high school students.

2.3. Blended Learning Importance

Based on a study, traditional platforms provide a more accurate assessment of student achievement than online ones do (Gupta, 2021). According to Schmidt et al. (2004), recent studies have shown the benefits of various technology-based instructional tools for efficient verbal and writing communication, so blended learning may be used in any area of education. However, not every student was against online learning. This shows how blended learning is an appropriate choice for the future. In order for students to swiftly adapt and be prepared to join online learning, a more thorough explanation of the online learning applications must be taken into consideration when conducting blended learning in the future. This needs to be taken consideration because students' self-efficacy decreases as a result of their lack of familiarity with using online learning tools, which makes students feel like they aren't as capable to compete academically with other students. According to Aladwan (2018), the respondent believes that adopting blended learning, which combines traditional in-class instruction with online learning, is more efficient than using one-way transmission of knowledge. Singh (2003) emphasized that in contrast to traditional e-learning, blended learning has more advantages and is more efficient.

However, research has shown that academicians have worries about using blended learning in their classes (Brooks, 2008).

The success of the blended training process was evaluated using five key scales that were identified based on the most recent online and blended learning literature. The learning curve, the assistance of the facilitator, the content, the teamwork, and the technology created these scales, Mouzakis et al. (2008). Technology and conventional learning are combined to create blended learning. It is an original, cutting-edge method that helps students achieve better in terms of knowledge, motivation, and satisfaction (Das, 2021). According to Birbal et al. (2018) the various learning styles of our students and teachers should be taken into account while designing the curriculum. For instance, the ratio of time spent in face-to-face and online sessions needs to be reconsidered to meet the various developmental needs of our students.

In blended learning strategies, there are some aspects that allow the students to measure their own performance. Every student can choose the method that is most suited to their needs from a wide variety of methods that greatly simplify the learning processes for numerous fields and concepts offers a lot of benefits, opportunities, and comforts to teachers (Boelens et al. 2017). An effective advantage of this learning process is that a blended learning approach allows the learner to communicate with the content at their own schedule. Students may benefit from the flexibility this learning process provides. Blended learning adoption can increase student satisfaction, lessen stress, and promote deeper learning.

2.4. The Attitude of Teachers and Students

The student-centered learning strategy known as blended learning, which is used by many teachers, can increase students' chances of learning. Maintaining communication, creativity, knowledge acquisition, and cooperation with students is essential for teachers in a blended learning environment. Blended learning helps students retain their critical thinking skills and mind-sets. Integrated motivation is a useful teaching philosophy that can help students in the blended learning process. On the other hand, defensive learning and adaptive learning must continue (Jowsey et al., 2020). To enhance the learner experience and teaching skills both of teachers and students, blended teaching methods and strategies were created.

On the other hand, programs in this area that empower teachers can improve the efficiency of online learning. Educational authorities can enhance the organizational and environmental conditions to support students by completely comprehending the variables influencing blended learning for the student viewpoint (Mirmoghtadaie et al., 2020).

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Participants

The researcher use nine participants from ten total students in the class for gaining the data; there were seven national students, one international student, and one lecturer of Master's Degree at the University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling in order to know students' and lecturer perspective related to the educational setting conducted in this University. The percentage of blended learning

was between the percentage of 60% online learning and 40% offline learning. The term "purposive sampling" refers to a group of non-probability sampling methods that select sample units depending on the availability of particular qualities.

3.2. Instruments

An open-ended questionnaire was used to gather the data for this descriptive case study. There were several questions to ask, such as; Effective Learning Platform Perspective, Satisfied Learning Platform Perspectives, Managing Time Learning Platform Perspective, Blended Learning Perspective, Future Educational Platform Perspective, and Comfortable Platform for Acquiring the Knowledge Perspective.

3.3. Data Collection

Open-ended questionnaires were used to collect data from the study's participants. Due to the participant's business and great distance, the researcher used Google form to make it efficient and effective. It is also simpler to answer the question completely. There was a link with six questions for the participants. The themes aim to know the student's perspective related to the best learning used, satisfied learning, time management, blended learning, appropriate future platform and their comfort levels with learning.

3.4. Data Analysis

The participants gathered and inputted the data by themselves. The data were split into three sections to simplify the analysis. The researcher used code as the Lecturer (L), International Student (IS), National Student (NS). According to Craswel (2009), there are six steps in analyzing the data collected which are described as follows: *First is organizing and preparing the data for analysis.* In this step involves transcribing interviews from Open-ended questionnaires, optically scanning material, typing up field notes, sorting and arranging the data into different types depending on the sources of information.

Second is reading through all the data. A first step is to obtain a general sense of the information and to reflect on its overall meaning.

The third is begun the detailed analysis with a coding process. It involves taking text data or pictures gathered during data collection, segmenting sentences (or paragraphs) or images into categories, and labeling those categories with a term, often a term based in the actual language of the participants.

Fourth is to use the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people as well as categories or themes for analysis. Description involves a detailed rendering of information about people, places, or events in a setting. Researchers can generate codes for this description. This analysis is useful in designing detailed descriptions for case studies, ethnographies, and narrative research projects.

Fifth is an advance how the description and themes will be represented in the qualitative narrative. The most popular approach is to use a narrative passage to convey the findings of the analysis. This might be a discussion that mentions a chronology of events, the detailed discussion of several themes or a discussion with interconnecting themes.

The final step is in data analysis involves making an interpretation or meaning of the data. Asking, "What were the lessons learned?". These lessons could be the researcher's personal interpretation, couched in the understanding that the inquirer brings to the study from her or his own culture, history, and experiences.

This study used a case study approach for data analysis. Based on the data collected from the participants, many pieces of information was investigated the student's perspective related to the best learning used, satisfied learning, time management, blended learning, appropriate future platform and their comfort levels with learning.

4. Findings

Lecturer and student's perspectives on blended learning in 40% offline and 60% online gave a better perspective towards educational setting. Here are the results from the open-ended questionnaire. The following are necessary with regard to certain themes:

4.1. Effective Learning Platform Perspective

Each learning platform had its own benefits and drawbacks. All of the participants demonstrated that the offline learning platform was superior to the online one because it delivered the following benefits: offline connection controlled learning environment with real classrooms, lack of cutting-edge technology, and qualification for a tangible presence at a specific location. Although it gave more flexibility in terms of time and location, online learning was also safer than offline learning since it could use a variety of digital tools and platforms to enhance interaction, such as discussion forums and video conferences.

- Lecturer

"Offline learning is effective way".

- International Student

"Online education is more secure than traditional instruction. On the other hand, offline learning is more efficient than online learning in terms of efficacy, and in my opinion, offline learning offers more advantages than online learning. For instance, Offline mode is out date in terms of technology. Online classes are a great way to learn about technological advancements. They are learning how to use digital and do it well by using computers or laptops and engaging with other students throughout a variety of channels".

- National Student

Respondent 1

"Both modes of learning have their advantages and disadvantages, and their effectiveness can vary based on some factors to consider when comparing the two: Flexibility and Accessibility: Online class learning provides greater flexibility in terms of time and location. Offline class learning, on the other hand, requires physical presence at a specific location".

Respondent 2

"Offline learning is efficient because I can get better understanding. Offline class learning offers a structured and controlled learning environment with physical classrooms".

Respondent 3

"When we have offline class, the students will get more understanding related to the material".

Respondent 4

"I prefer to choose offline because it provides face-to-face interaction between students and instructors".

Respondent 5

"Offline learning is more effective because we won't get internet connection distraction".

Respondent 6

"Offline is better for undergraduate students because we can get more understanding".

Respondent 7

"Online is more effective because the time is more flexible and easier to be accessed".

4.2. Satisfied Learning Platform Perspectives

According to the respondents, students were satisfied with offline learning because they could access more knowledge and a deeper understanding through the teacher's body language and the voices of other students. Additionally, there was a chance to connect with students from various backgrounds to solve problems. Offline instruction may also improve social interaction and motivation among pupils. Additionally, the lecturer loved using both platforms while the students effectively discussed and shared material.

- **Lecturer**

"Discussion with my students is fun. We can share the information together and it is two way learning".

- **International Student**

"Because you can access more information and have a deeper comprehension through the instructor's body language and that of the other students, I prefer offline classes. You may communicate, work together on issues, and network with other students from all backgrounds. I may have loved offline classes because I earned my bachelor's degree through them. The only way to learn a subject more thoroughly is in traditional classroom settings increased participation and interpersonal contact".

- **National Student**

Respondent 1

"I tend to feel satisfied with offline. Offline class learning provides face-to-face interaction between students and instructors".

Respondent 2

"Offline because we can meet with the lecturer and friends to discuss each other".

Respondent 3

"Our focus will increase when we have offline learning. This direct engagement often enhances student motivation, social interaction, and the opportunity for immediate clarification of concepts".

Respondent 4

"I prefer online class because there is more interaction between the students and lecturers when learning in person. They get to take part in additional classroom exercises".

Respondent 5

"Offline class can facilitates the students in order to get real-time discussions, directly feedback, and collaborative activities".

Respondent 6

"Offline learning because we can be more focus without any distraction around".

Respondent 7

"Offline learning is better because we can get directly feedback each other both students and teacher".

4.3. Managing Time Learning Platform Perspective

No matter how well we could modify and manage the time, it wasn't a problem. Some of the students had jobs at their school, thus blended learning was still relevant as long as the course was based on the scheduling agreement. Another respondent, on the other hand, claimed that taking classes online posed problems in poor time management because of the lack of a schedule, the number of distractions, and the multitasking.

- **Lecturer**

"All learning methods have their drawbacks long as we can adjust it, there is nothing hard to manage".

- **International Student**

"I think it's hard to manage time for online class. One of the biggest issues online students have is poor scheduling. Lack of a schedule, a lot of distractions, and multitasking can all contribute to poor time management. Lack of a specific place to work is another issue that could result in ineffective time management".

- **National Student**

Respondent 1

"As long there is a schedule I have no problem with both methods".

Respondent 2

"Managing online learning is better than offline, because every time and everywhere we can access the class".

Respondent 3

"Online learning is easier than offline because we just provide zoom link and power point".

Respondent 4

"We must mix online and offline learning with the same percentage".

Respondent 5

"Managing time is better for online learning but managing condition is better for offline learning".

Respondent 6

"Online learning is manageable".

Respondent 7

"I prefer online learning to be managed because we just prepare zoom and laptop".

4.4. Blended Learning Perspective

Because it might improve students' understanding and comprehension, every respondent concurred that integrated learning was the ideal strategy. When taking classes online, students could learn through independent research, group projects, and access to a variety of digital resources. Additionally, offline learning was used to transfer the knowledge that had been learned to the other students and lecturers. Blended learning at UMP was an effective strategy and useful platform that could increase student enthusiasm, encourage engagement and support a range of learning demands.

- **Lecturer**

"It is good way, students have more time to have autonomous learning".

- **International Student**

"I think it's good because in online class you'll get information and in offline you'll share about your understanding so this is the best choice from UMP because in the same time we get skills from online and offline".

- **National Student**

Respondent 1

"Blended learning offers several potential benefits. It allows students to access course materials and engage in online activities at their own pace and convenience, fostering self-directed learning. . It can cater to different learning styles, promote active engagement, and accommodate diverse student needs. In the case of the blended learning lessons held at UMP for master's degree students with a 60% online and 40% offline distribution, it suggests a significant reliance on online components".

Respondent 2

"By combining both online and offline elements, blended learning seeks to leverage the strengths of each mode of instruction".

Respondent 3

"I agree with blended learning because it is a simple way to combine learning and working".

Respondent 4

"Blended learning, which combines both online and offline components, has gained popularity in educational settings due to its potential to offer a flexible and dynamic learning experience".

Respondent 5

"Mix method is not effective. I prefer to choose offline learning for more being active in the class".

Respondent 6

"Yes it's better but still if the lecturer only gives task without any explanation through offline class, it will be poor".

Respondent 7

"Mix method is a perfect learning because we can manage our business each other".

4.5. Future Educational Platform Perspective

The best option for enhancing educational settings in the future was blended learning since it was effective at mixing offline and online learning strategies, each of which provided benefits including a self-autonomous, adaptable, and dynamic learning experience. The potential benefits of online learning, according to another student, include greater free time, a wider range of possibilities for education, and reduced costs.

- **Lecturer**

"I have finished my doctorate degree, so no more".

- **International Student**

"Of course depending to time I would like to pursue online classes. Nowadays we are developing fast Alhamdulillah so for future demand online class is better. Some of the advantages of online learning that I wanted to discuss here are flexibility, reduced expenses, more free time, more course variety, job progression chances, more cooperation, personalized education, and improved time management skills".

- **National Student**

Respondent 1

"Online components can provide a platform for interactive discussions, collaborative projects, and access to a wide range of digital resources".

Respondent 2

"Online class learning utilizes various digital tools and platforms to facilitate interaction, such as discussion forums, video conferencing, and collaborative virtual spaces".

Respondent 3

"Online class learning relies on digital resources, including e-books, online databases, and multimedia materials. In conclusion, the choice between the two I tend to choose offline".

Respondent 4

"Online learning is more effective for postgraduate students because they can separate time to work and learning".

Respondent 5

"Nowadays, technology is increased. I think online learning will be increased".

Respondent 6

"Online learning is good in the feature because we can get knowledge everywhere".

Respondent 7

"Offline learning we can access the technology wider".

4.6. Comfortable Platform for Acquiring the Knowledge Perspective

Having information was a key objective that supported student achievement. When blended learning was implemented, all of the respondents claimed they feel secure and at ease because theoretical information without application is not good knowledge. Through online classes, they were able to put their theoretical knowledge and share the knowledge into practice in offline class. Additionally, since almost all students work, they should set apart certain times for both work and study so that blended learning can promote teamwork and social engagement through both online and offline activities. A learner can expand their knowledge through every kind of learning. Moreover, by offline learning it wouldn't be a trouble connection.

- **Lecturer**

"All types of learning that can accommodate students to increase their knowledge".

- **International Student**

"I think the way of teaching in UMP as you mentioned it before blended learning is comfort because theoretical knowledge without practice is not good knowledge and we can forget but if we get theoretically knowledge and we practice it in offline class our knowledge will be fixed up in our mind for a an extended period of and at the same time we're not behind world demand".

- **National Student**

Respondent 1

"I personally agree with blended learning as I am a student who works as well. Blended learning fosters collaboration and social interaction through both online and offline activities. Learners can interact with peers, exchange ideas, and work in virtual teams through online forums, group projects, and teamwork activities".

Respondent 2

"When acquiring the knowledge, offline learning is better because we can be more focus".

Respondent 3

"Online platform can make us to explore the confidence by online but we must manage our focus".

Respondent 4

"Offline learning can meet and discuss together".

Respondent 5

"Offline learning can't meet device trouble when learning".

Respondent 6

"Offline is better because we can make a good interaction in order to get more understanding".

Respondent 7

"I think offline is understandable. It can enhance collaboration and communication skills".

5. Discussion

Based on the results above, there are three discussions addressed:

5.1. Viewpoint of Online and Offline Learning

Because offline learning gave them access to more information, a deeper understanding of concepts, and connections with peers from other backgrounds, students were happy with it. The social connection and motivation of students may both be enhanced through offline instruction. While students efficiently talked and shared content, the instructor appreciated using both platforms. However, online learning also could enhance student to be more flexible in terms of scheduling and location. Develop students to use a variety of digital tools and platforms, like discussion boards, video conferencing, and collaborative virtual environments. It is in line with research by Bestari, A., C., et al. (2023) stated that teaching English online through the media can stimulate their competence to find vocabulary to get good sentences in their texts. In a learning environment, online databases, e-books, and multimedia materials are just a few of the digital resources.

5.2. Viewpoint of Blended Learning

Based on the finding, the entire participants gave a good opinion related to blended learning that was implemented at University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto. Students could learn autonomously online or offline learning. As long as the student was interested to join the class, it was not a big problem to manage the time because the students and lecturer have made a scheduling agreement. Both educational settings also provided a method for acquiring knowledge and a discussion platform, so the student could be active in sharing the knowledge. By using a mixed learning approach, students' progress can be increased (Das ,2021). It helped the students enhance their knowledge by using mixing method platform.5'

Regarding their perceptions of the entire blended learning environment, students were asked seven questions. According to Alsalhi et al. (2019), respondents believed it would increase student engagement in learning processes, increase the importance of responsibility in learning, the reputation of the institutions where it was used would be improved, make the learning environment more flexible. This existing research also related with the finding in this research that showed the ability to put theoretical information into practice and discuss it in offline classrooms makes blended learning a pleasant environment

for knowledge acquisition. As students work and learn at the same time, this strategy encourages collaboration and social interaction. Through online discussions, group projects, and virtual teamwork, blended learning encourages social engagement and collaboration, allowing students to connect with one another, share ideas, and build knowledge together. Blended learning is viewed as an excellent method for students to enhance their knowledge and talents, and both local and international students are in favor of this strategy.

5.3. Viewpoint of Platform used at University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto

The goal of the study was to comprehend how lecturers and students felt about blended learning, which involves 40% offline and 60% online. Due to its face-to-face connection, controlled learning environment, lack of cutting-edge technology, and demand for a tangible presence at a specified place, the results demonstrated that offline learning was superior. Due to the use of digital tools and platforms to improve engagement, online learning was also safer.

As long as the course was built around the scheduling agreement, managing time wasn't an issue for blended learning. However, due to distractions, lack of a timetable, and multitasking, some students struggled with poor time management. As it allowed students to acquire material course and participate in online activities at their own pace and convenience, blended learning was the ideal choice for enhancing students' understanding and comprehension and encouraging self-directed learning.

6. Conclusion

Online and offline learning offer students access to more information, deeper understanding of concepts, and connections with peers from different backgrounds. Offline instruction enhances social connection and motivation, while online learning allows students to be more flexible in scheduling and location.

Students believe, blended learning increases student engagement, emphasizes responsibility, improves institutions' reputation, and makes the learning environment more flexible. This strategy encourages collaboration and social interaction, allowing students to connect with one another, share ideas, and build knowledge together. From the participants support blended learning as an effective way to advance their knowledge and abilities.

The study at the University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto used blended learning online and offline with a percentage of 60% and 40% was effective and appropriate. Students and lecturers enjoyed both of the platforms. Mixing both of them could help the students in acquiring knowledge and also enhance the students' achievement autonomously. Moreover, almost all students work at some institution, so they should define the time for learning and working. Blended learning was the best problem solution to engage students' motivation, achievement, and timing in line the schedule based on time agreements both students and lecturers before.

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